

INVESTIGATION OF FIBER REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE WITH A CIRCULAR HOLE

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ABSTRACT

Static tensile behavior of an unidirectional ceramic matrix composite with a circular hole was investigated. Different hole diameter, D , to specimen width, W , ratios ranging from 0.1 to 0.4 were tested. The effect of hole, for all sizes, was almost negligible, and the notched strength was found to be almost equal to the net section strength.

Keywords: Fiber-reinforced Ceramic Matrix Composite, Notched Strength, Hole-Size Effect.

INTRODUCTION

Materials engineers have long sought materials with high strength and stability at elevated temperatures. The demand for such high performance materials is increasing rapidly with the push for hypersonic flight and other advanced aerospace applications. Many ceramic and glasses possess the high strength and stability at high temperature, but are notorious for their inherent notch-sensitive characteristics. However the recent development of fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites has generated much interest among materials scientists [1-8]. Fiber reinforcement offers tougher materials and increased strain at fracture. For general engineering usage, notch-sensitive characteristics of these fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites should be addressed. As a first step in this direction, the hole-size effects on these composite were investigated in a fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composite with unidirectional lay-up containing a circular hole. The specific tasks undertaken in this study were: 1) to measure the effect of hole size on the static tensile strength, and 2) to document the damage mechanisms from a circular hole in these composites. The present study is confined to the room temperature only.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The ceramic composite employed in this study was aluminosilicate glass ceramic matrix reinforced with silicon carbide fibers designated as SiC/1723. The fiber reinforcement was continuous Tyranno fiber developed by Ube Corporation, Japan. Tyranno is basically a silicon carbide fiber modified with the addition of titanium. The matrix material was a silicate glass manufactured by Corning Glass Works with code name of 1723. The material was pre-pregged into unidirectional lamina. The final composite plate was obtained by hot pressing these pre-pregged plies with the unidirectional lay-up. These plates were fabricated at the Air Force Materials Laboratory, Wright-Patterson Air

Force Base. The nominal composite plate thickness was 2.5 mm. The nominal fiber volume fraction was measured to be equal to 0.45. Straight-edged specimens were cut from these plates with a low-speed diamond wafering saw to minimize edge damage. All specimens were 101.6 mm in length with a gage length of 50.8 mm.

The specimen width and hole diameter were varied from 0.5 cm to 1.3 cm, and 0.1 cm to 0.2 cm, respectively. This provided a hole diameter, D , to specimen width, W , ratios from 0.1 to 0.4 in different specimens. The holes were drilled with an ultrasonic drilling machine, then polished on the inner surface to minimize the possibility of pre-existing machining defects. To polish the holes, brass rods were turned down to a diameter that would fit tightly in the drilled holes, then roughened slightly. These rods were used in a drill press with 25 micron lapping compound followed by 9 micron diamond suspension compound. This provided a smooth and defect-free hole in the specimen. The fiberglass tabs were glued on each end of the specimen to eliminate grip-induced damage.

All tests were conducted in a laboratory air environment at room temperature (approximately 21°C). While the test was underway, replicas were taken periodically from the face of the specimen to observe damage in the area around the circumference of hole.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the notched strength as a function of diameter to width ratio. The notched strength is defined as ultimate load divided by notched cross-sectional area at the hole. Further, this notched strength is normalized by dividing it by the average value of unnotched strength. Figure 1 also shows the net strength based on notched cross-sectional area of the specimen without any consideration of the stress-concentration due the presence of hole, and this will be horizontal line in the figure. The notched strength of specimens with hole do not exhibit a rapid decline from its counterpart in specimens with no hole, as would be expected in an isotropic material (due to the stress concentration induced by the hole). This indicates a high degree of notch insensitivity. The notched strength do, however, drop slightly below the line of net strength. At the maximum D/W ratio of 0.4, the notched strength from the best-fit curve is 84 percent of the value on the line of net strength. Since the net strength line equates to the average no-hole ultimate stress applied to the notched cross-sectional area, this can be interpreted as a 16 percent notch sensitivity at $D/W = 0.4$. This behavior in ceramic matrix composite resembles with its counterpart in the unidirectional polymeric composite. For example, Tan's tests with the unidirectional graphite/epoxy showed no variation in the notched strength and net strength [9]. The damage initiation and progression mechanisms, as discussed next, provides the explanation for this behavior of notch insensitivity in the tested ceramic matrix composite.

The damage initiated in the form of four cracks at the periphery of the hole at locations with an angle θ from the axis normal to the load, as shown schematically in Figure 2. These cracks in all tests emanated from the hole at an average value of $\theta = 65$ degrees (θ varied from 70 to 60 degrees), and not at the theoretical maximum stress concentration points, A and B. These cracks grew radially outward for a very short distance and, then longitudinally parallel to fibers to the end of the specimen or until the failure occurred at the unnotched cross-sectional area of specimen due to the reduced cross-sectional area of specimen. The initiation and progression of these cracks were obtaining by examining periodically specimens with the acetate replication technique on the face of the specimen. Figure 3 is a typical replicate photograph showing the initiation and progression of these two cracks on one side of the hole. These cracks as seen on the replicate were not the surface cracks but extended completely through the thickness of the specimen. This was verified by sectioning a few specimens (which did not fail but had a crack growth near the hole) in a manner which provided the interior view along thickness of specimen. Further it was, on closer examination, evident that the

fiber exposed by the cracks near the hole were still intact. A typical close-up of the fractured surface is shown in Figure 4. The stress level at which the crack initiation occurred was estimated to be about the one-half of ultimate strength for all specimens with different D/W ratios, since it was very difficult to pinpoint the actual instant of initiation of these small cracks.

SUMMARY

A study was conducted to investigate the hole size effect of an unidirectional silicon carbide fiber reinforced aluminosilicate glass ceramic composite, SiC/1723, with a center hole subjected to the static tensile loading. The hole size was varied from diameter, D, to specimen width, W, ratio ranging from 0.1 to 0.4. The notched strength was found to be almost equal to the net section strength regardless of the hole diameter-to-width ratio, thus showing that the tested ceramic matrix composite was a very mildly notch sensitive. The damage mechanism involved the initiation of four cracks at the periphery of the hole at locations with an average angle $\theta = 65$ degrees from the axis normal to the load, and then the progression of these cracks parallel to the fibers.

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Figure 1. Notched strength as function of diameter to width ratio

Figure 2. Schematic view of crack growth from hole

Figure 3. Crack initiation from hole

Figure 4. Close-up of fractured specimen